

COPERNICUS
MARINE ENVIRONMENT MONITORING SERVICE

QUALITY INFORMATION DOCUMENT

North West European Shelf Production Centre NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_004_013

Issue: 1.3

Contributors: M. Tonani, D. Bruciaferri, C. Pequignet, R. King, P. Sykes, N. McConnell, J. Siddorn

Approval date by the CMEMS product quality coordination team: 08/01/2021

QUID for NWS MFC Products NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_004_013	Ref: CMEMS-NWS-QUID-004-013 Date: 10 Sep 2020 Issue: 1.3
---	--

CHANGE RECORD

When the quality of the products changes, the Quid is updated and a row is added to this table. The third column specifies which sections or sub-sections have been updated. The fourth column should mention the version of the product to which the change applies.

Issue	Date	§	Description of Change	Author	Validated By
1.0	12/09/2018	All	First release	M. Tonani, C. Pequignet, R. King, P. Sykes, N. McConnell, J. Siddorn	J. Polton and I. Golbeck
			Review		Mercator Ocean
1.1	06/02/2019		Small corrections	M. Tonani	
	25/04/2019				Mercator Ocean
1.2	29/08/2019		Small corrections and updated reference	M.Tonani	I. Ascione
	11/10/19		Review		Mercator Ocean
1.3	10/09/2020		Science Update – Coupled Ocean-Wave Model. Addition of IV.9 SST forecast skills section.	M. Tonani, D. Bruciaferri	I. Ascione

QUID for NWS MFC Products NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_004_013	Ref: CMEMS-NWS-QUID-004-013 Date: 10 Sep 2020 Issue: 1.3
---	--

TABLE OF CONTENTS

<i>I</i>	<i>Executive summary</i>	7
	1.1 Products covered by this document	7
	1.2 Summary of the results	7
	1.3 Estimated Accuracy Numbers	9
<i>II</i>	<i>Production system description</i>	10
	II.1 Production centres name	10
	II.2 Production system name	10
	II.3 Description of the target version	10
	II.3.1 FOAM AMM15: model components, region, grid and bathymetry	14
	II.3.2 Physical model.....	16
	II.3.3 Assimilation method	16
<i>III</i>	<i>Validation framework</i>	18
	III.1 Summary of tested metrics	19
<i>IV</i>	<i>Validation results</i>	20
	IV.1 Observations used for the validation	20
	IV.2 Bathymetry	22
	IV.3 Tidal harmonics	22
	IV.3.1 Comparison with tide gauges	22
	IV.3.2 Comparison with HF Radar	25
	IV.4 Sea surface temperature (SST)	28
	IV.4.1 Comparison with in-situ	28
	IV.4.2 Variability in SST against in situ	29
	IV.4.3 Comparison to OSTIA	32
	IV.5 Temperature and salinity profiles	33
	IV.6 Mixed Layer Depth	38
	IV.7 Sea Surface Height	39
	IV.8 Surface currents	41
<i>V</i>	<i>System’s Noticeable events, outages or changes</i>	43
<i>VI</i>	<i>Quality changes since previous version</i>	44
<i>VII</i>	<i>References</i>	46

QUID for NWS MFC Products NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_004_013	Ref:	CMEMS-NWS-QUID-004-013
	Date:	10 Sep 2020
	Issue:	1.3

TABLE OF FIGURES

FIGURE 1: FOAM PRODUCTION CYCLE. 10

FIGURE 2: FOAM AMM15 BATHYMETRY (M) SHOWING THE MODEL DOMAIN (INDICATED BY THE SHADED REGION). THE YELLOW BOX IS THE DOMAIN COVERED BY THE REGULAR GRID AMM15 PRODUCT DELIVERED TO CMEMS. THE RED LINE IS THE MODEL AND PRODUCT DOMAIN OF AMM7 (NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHYS_004_001_B. FIGURED MODIFIED FROM GRAHAM ET AL. 2018. 15

FIGURE 3: TOTAL NUMBER OF TEMPERATURE (LEFT) AND SALINITY (RIGHT) PROFILES IN 2-DEGREE BINS FOR 2016-2017. TOP PANEL: OBSERVATIONS DISTRIBUTION IN WINTER (DECEMBER-JANUARY-FEBRUARY, DJF). BOTTOM PANEL: OBSERVATIONS DISTRIBUTION IN SUMMER (JUNE-JULY-AUGUST, JJA)..... 20

FIGURE 4: MAPS OF THE INDEPENDENT OBSERVATIONS USED FOR VALIDATION. MASSMO4 GLIDERS ARE BLUE, COSYNA HF IN THE GERMAN BIGHT IN GREEN AND THE MOORING IN THE GERMAN BIGHT IN RED. 21

FIGURE 5: NUMBER OF OBSERVATIONS (2016-2017) USED BY THE DATA ASSIMILATION AND BY THE VALIDATION. SST (IN SITU AND SATELLITE), LEFT PANEL. SATELLITE SLA RIGHT PANEL..... 21

FIGURE 6: MODEL BATHYMETRY ON SHELF. LEFT: AMM7, RIGHT: AMM15. 22

FIGURE 7: RMSD AND BIAS (OBSERVATION-MODEL) OF THE TIDAL AMPLITUDE (TOP PANEL) AND PHASE (BOTTOM PANEL) OF THE PREVALENT TIDAL CONSTITUENTS. AMM15 IS IN RED (DOTTED LINE BIAS, FULL LINE RMSD) AND AMM7 IN BLUE (DOTTED LINE BIAS, FULL LINE RMSD). THE VALUES ARE MEANS OF ALL THE AVAILABLE TIDE GAUGES..... 23

FIGURE 8: M2 PHASE (LEFT) AND AMPLITUDE (RIGHT) ERROR RELATIVE TO OBSERVATIONS FOR AMM15 (OBSERVATION-MODEL)..... 24

FIGURE 9: M2 AMPLITUDE (LEFT) AND PHASE (RIGHT) OBSERVATIONS VERSUS MODEL VALUES. 24

FIGURE 10; CO-TIDAL CHART FOR M2 COMPONENT, AMM15. 25

FIGURE 11: PLOTS OF STATISTICS BETWEEN HF RADAR SURFACE CURRENT OBSERVATIONS AND AMM7 (LEFT) AND AMM15 (RIGHT) FOR THE HIGH-PASSED FILTERED DATA (TIDAL SIGNAL). BIAS (OBSERVATION-MODEL) AND RMSD (IN M/S) ARE ESTIMATED ON THE VELOCITY VECTOR MAGNITUDES. 26

FIGURE 12: PLOTS OF VECTOR CORRELATION AMPLITUDE (TOP) AND PHASE OR VEERING (BOTTOM). POSITIVE (NEGATIVE) VEERING REPRESENT A CLOCKWISE (COUNTER-CLOCKWISE) ANGLE OF AMM15 VECTORS WITH RESPECT TO THE HF RADAR VECTORS. 27

FIGURE 13: OBSERVATION MINUS MODEL SST DAILY ASSESSMENT OF AMM15 (BLACK) AND AMM7 (BLUE) AGAINST IN-SITU OBSERVATIONS (TOP PLOT) AND NUMBER OF OBSERVATIONS PER DAY (BOTTOM PLOT) FOR THE WHOLE DOMAIN. IN THE TOP-PLOT, THE MEAN ERROR (OBSERVATION-MODEL) IS SHOWN BY THE DASHED LINE (A POSITIVE VALUE INDICATES A COLD MODEL BIAS) AND THE RMSD ERROR IS SHOWN BY THE SOLID LINE..... 28

QUID for NWS MFC Products NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_004_013	Ref:	CMEMS-NWS-QUID-004-013
	Date:	10 Sep 2020
	Issue:	1.3

FIGURE 14: TIMESERIES OF SEA SURFACE TEMPERATURE (LEFT) AND FILTERED SST (RIGHT) FOR THE FINO 3 BUOY FOR DECEMBER2016-FEBRUARY 2017 (TOP) AND JUNE-AUGUST 2017 (BOTTOM)..... 30

FIGURE 15: POWER SPECTRUM OF SST FOR THE FINO3 BUOY COMPARED WITH THE AMM7 (BLUE) AND AMM15 (RED) SIMULATIONS FOR DECEMBER 2016 TO FEBRUARY 207 (TOP LEFT), MARCH TO MAY 2017 (TOP RIGHT), JUNE TO AUGUST 2017 (BOTTOM LEFT) AND SEPTEMBER TO NOVEMBER 2017 (BOTTOM RIGHT). 31

FIGURE 16: MODEL SST MINUS OSTIA RMD AND BIAS DAILY COMPARISON FOR AMM7 (BLUE) AND AMM15 (RED) FOR THE WHOLE DOMAIN (NEGATIVE MEAN ERROR INDICATES A WARM MODEL BIAS)..... 32

FIGURE 17: OBSERVATION MINUS MODEL TEMPERATURE (LEFT) AND SALINITY (RIGHT) PROFILE ASSESSMENT FOR AMM15 (BLACK) AND AMM7 (BLUE) FOR THE WHOLE DOMAIN (LEFT PLOT). THE RMS DIFFERENCE IS SHOWN BY THE SOLID LINES AND BIAS (OBSERVATION-MODEL) IS SHOWN BY THE DASHED LINES. 33

FIGURE 18: OBSERVATION-MODEL AS YEARLY MEAN RMSD AND BIAS AT THE 5 MOORINGS IN THE GERMAN BIGHT. TEMPERATURE (LEFT) AND SALINITY (RIGHT) AT THE SURFACE AND AT THE BOTTOM. THE RED LINE IS AMM15, THE BLUE LINE IS AMM7..... 34

FIGURE 19: SEA BOTTOM TEMPERATURE AT THE FINO3 MOORING FOR YEAR 2017. AMM15 RED LINE, AMM7 BLUE LINE, OBSERVATIONS BLACK LINE. 34

FIGURE 20: SEA SURFACE SALINITY AT THE NSBII MOORING FOR YEAR 2017. AMM15 RED LINE, AMM7 BLUE LINE, OBSERVATIONS BLACK LINE. 35

FIGURE 21: GLIDER 553-100 TRAJECTORY. THE GLIDER STARTED THE MEASUREMENT CLOSE TO THE SCOTLAND COAST, THEN MOVED TOWARDS THE SHELF BREAK. 36

FIGURE 22: TEMPERATURE PROFILE ALONG GLIDER 553-100 TRAJECTORY. TOP PANEL: TEMPERATURE MEASURED BY THE GLIDER. BOTTOM LEFT: DIFFERENCE GLIDER-AMM15. BOTTOM RIGHT: DIFFERENCE GLIDER-AMM7.THE VERTICAL BLUE LINE REPRESENTS WHEN THE GLIDER GOES OVER THE SHELF BREAK, CROSSING THE 200 M ISOBATH. BEFORE THAT TIME THE GLIDER IS ON THE SHELF. 36

FIGURE 23: SALINITY PROFILE ALONG GLIDER 553-100 TRAJECTORY. TOP PANEL: SALINITY MEASURED BY THE GLIDER. BOTTOM LEFT: DIFFERENCE GLIDER-AMM15. BOTTOM RIGHT: DIFFERENCE GLIDER-AMM7.THE VERTICAL BLUE LINE REPRESENTS WHEN THE GLIDER GOES OVER THE SHELF BREAK, CROSSING THE 200 M ISOBATH. BEFORE THAT TIME THE GLIDER IS ON THE SHELF. 37

FIGURE 24: DENSITY PROFILE ALONG GLIDER 553-100 TRAJECTORY. TOP PANEL: SALINITY MEASURED BY THE GLIDER. BOTTOM LEFT: DIFFERENCE GLIDER-AMM15. BOTTOM RIGHT: DIFFERENCE GLIDER-AMM7.THE VERTICAL BLUE LINE REPRESENTS WHEN THE GLIDER GOES OVER THE SHELF BREAK, CROSSING THE 200 M ISOBATH. BEFORE THAT TIME THE GLIDER IS ON THE SHELF. 37

FIGURE 25: LEFT PANEL: SPATIAL DISTRIBUTION OF THE N4 OBSERVATIONS USED FOR THE MLD COMPUTATION. RIGHT PANEL: AMM15 KARA MIXED LAYER DEPTH BIAS (RED DASHED) AND RMSD (BLUE SOLID). A POSITIVE MEAN ERROR VALUE INDICATES A MODEL OVER-ESTIMATE. A POSITIVE BIAS VALUE INDICATES A MODEL UNDER-ESTIMATION OF THE MLD..... 38

FIGURE 26: MIXED LAYER DEPTH ALONG THE GLIDER 553 TRANSECT. BLACK LINE: GLIDER OBSERVATION, RED AMM15, BLUE AMM7. THE VERTICAL BLUE LINE REPRESENTS WHEN THE GLIDER GOES OVER THE SHELF BREAK, CROSSING THE 200 M ISOBATH. BEFORE THAT TIME THE GLIDER IS ON THE SHELF. 39

<p style="text-align: center;"> QUID for NWS MFC Products NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_004_013 </p>	<p>Ref:</p> <p>Date:</p> <p>Issue:</p>	<p>CMEMS-NWS-QUID-004-013</p> <p>10 Sep 2020</p> <p>1.3</p>
--	--	---

FIGURE 27: OBSERVATION MINUS MODEL SSH DAILY ASSESSMENT OF AMM15 (BLACK) AND AMM7 (BLUE) AGAINST SATELLITE OBSERVATIONS (TOP PLOT OF EACH PANEL) AND NUMBER OF OBSERVATIONS PER DAY (BOTTOM PLOT OF EACH PANEL) FOR THE CONTINENTAL SHELF REGION (TOP PANEL) AND THE OFF SHELF (BOTTOM PANEL). THE MEAN ERROR IS SHOWN BY THE DASHED LINE AND THE RMS ERROR IS SHOWN BY THE SOLID LINE..... 40

FIGURE 28: MARCH 2017 AVERAGE SURFACE FLOW FOR HF RADAR (TOP), AMM7 (MIDDLE) AND AMM15 (BOTTOM), FROM TONANI ET AL. (2019). MODEL DATA ARE RE-GRIDDED ON THE HF RADAR GRID USING CUBIC INTERPOLATION. THE HOURLY MODEL OUTPUTS ARE LINEARLY INTERPOLATED EVERY MINUTE TO MATCH THE HF RADAR OBSERVATIONS. MODEL OUTPUT ARE ONLY PLOTTED WHERE HF RADAR DATA ARE AVAILABLE. 41

<p style="text-align: center;">QUID for NWS MFC Products</p> <p style="text-align: center;">NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_004_013</p>	<p>Ref:</p> <p>Date:</p> <p>Issue:</p>	<p>CMEMS-NWS-QUID-004-013</p> <p>10 Sep 2020</p> <p>1.3</p>
--	--	---

I EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

I.1 Products covered by this document

This document refers to the following real-time CMEMS products:

- NORTHWESTSHELF-ANALYSIS-FORECAST-PHY-004-013. The physical component of the North West European Analysis and Forecast system at ~1.5 km horizontal resolution and 33 vertical levels.

I.2 Summary of the results

The quality NWS forecast system (AMM15) has been assessed using two-year trial experiments (years 2016-2017). The results are compared to observations and AMM7, the existing NWS forecast system.

AMM15 is the first very high-resolution forecast system implemented in this area. The system resolves fine scale structures and variability better than the AMM7.

Validation at basin scale and using daily means penalises the high-resolution system and the Estimated Accuracy Numbers, which are similar between the two systems, do not reflect the AMM15 system's superior performance. AMM15 performs better than the AMM7 when validated against high resolution observations, in small geographical areas (Tonani et al., 2019, <https://doi.org/10.5194/os-15-1133-2019>).

Tides: The tides are accurate across most of the domain: the RMS error for M2 amplitude is 12cm. The main exceptions are in the Irish Sea and Southern Bight of the North Sea, where the model amplitudes are somewhat too low.

Temperature (SST): SST data is assimilated by this system, so surface errors are small with a mean error of -0.01 °C off shelf and -0.02°C on shelf (a warm bias) and RMS error of 0.48°C and 0.54 °C respectively. The model warm bias is stronger on-shelf than off-shelf.

Temperature (profiles): Averaged over the whole water column the RMS error is 0.43°C and the bias (obs-model) is 0.02°C. The sparse observations on the shelf suggest the model has a small cold bias with a relatively uniform RMS error. The comparison with high resolution observations shows a very good agreement between the model and the observations.

Salinity: The mean salinity bias (obs-model) averaged over the whole region is very small, -0.01 (the model is slightly saltier than the observations). The mean RMS difference over the whole region is 0.11 (measured on the Practical Salinity Unit scale). The comparison with high resolution observations shows a very good improvement in the model, compared to the previous version.

Mixed layer depth: Data for the assessment was generally sparse. Model errors were small during the spring/summer months and larger during winter when data was sparser. The model tends to over-estimate the mixed layer depth. The MLD bias and RMSD in summer are better than in the previous system. This is confirmed also from the validation against very high-resolution observations.

QUID for NWS MFC Products NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_004_013	Ref: Date: Issue:	CMEMS-NWS-QUID-004-013 10 Sep 2020 1.3
---	-------------------------	--

Sea Surface Height: The SSH has a higher RMS and mean error on shelf, than off shelf. The RMS is less than 0.1 m off-shelf and slightly above on-shelf. This is expected because SSH is assimilated only in areas with a depth higher than 700 m and on shelf the signal is dominated by tides.

QUID for NWS MFC Products NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_004_013	Ref:	CMEMS-NWS-QUID-004-013
	Date:	10 Sep 2020
	Issue:	1.3

I.3 Estimated Accuracy Numbers

Table 1: Estimated accuracy numbers

Variable	Location	Supporting observations	RMS Difference		Mean Error (observation-model)	
			AMM7v9	AMM15v2	AMM7v9	AMM15v2
M2 tidal harmonic (amplitude)	Full domain	Tide gauge data	10.4 cm	9.8 cm	-0.2 cm	-4.6 cm
M2 tidal harmonic (phase)	Full domain	Tide gauge data	12.4°	12.3°	-2 °	4.2°
SST	Full domain	In situ observations	0.45°C	0.48°C	-0.01°C	-0.01°C
	Continental shelf	In situ observations	0.51°C	0.54°C	-0.02°C	-0.02°C
SST	Full domain	OSTIA satellite L4	0.34°C	0.34°C	-0.06	-0.08
T profiles	Full domain	In situ observations	0.47°C	0.43°C	-0.04°C	0.02°C
S profiles	Full domain	In situ observations	0.13 PSU	0.11 PSU	0.01 PSU	-0.01 PSU
SSH	Off-shelf	Altimeter from satellite	0.09 m	0.09 m	-0.01 m	0.01 m
	Continental shelf	Altimeter from satellite	0.13 m	0.11 m	-0.06 m	-0.02 m
Mixed layer depth	Full domain	In situ observations	N/A	122 m	N/A	22 m
	Full domain Period: May-Oct	In situ observations	N/A	22 m	N/A	-11 m

QUID for NWS MFC Products NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_004_013	Ref:	CMEMS-NWS-QUID-004-013
	Date:	10 Sep 2020
	Issue:	1.3

II PRODUCTION SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

II.1 Production centres name

North-West Shelf MFC -Met Office, UK.

II.2 Production system name

North-West European Shelf Physics Analysis and Forecast (NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_004_013).

Met Office – FOAM (Forecasting Ocean Assimilation) Shelf Seas Atlantic Margin Model 1.5 km (AMM15)

II.3 Description of the target version

This document details the quality of the products from the FOAM Shelf Seas –Atlantic Margin Model at 1.5 km of horizontal resolution. This system is an upgrade of the previous system at 7 km of resolution. The 1.5 km system has a slightly different domain and therefore the lateral boundaries are located in a different geographical location. Table 2 presents a summary of the differences. This system has been subjected to an update in December 2020 in which the model is coupled to the wave model producing NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_WAV_004_014. The coupling terms are:

- Modification of water-side surface stress on the ocean by wave growth and dissipation
- Stokes-Coriolis force in the momentum equation
- Wave-height-dependent ocean surface roughness

The coupling frequency is hourly.

The FOAM system is delivering everyday 2-day analysis (Best Estimate and NRT analysis) and 6-day of forecast, Figure 1.

Figure 1: FOAM production cycle.

QUID for NWS MFC Products NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_004_013	Ref: CMEMS-NWS-QUID-004-013 Date: 10 Sep 2020 Issue: 1.3
---	--

Table 2: differences between NORTHWESTSHELF-ANALYSIS-FORECAST-PHY-004-013 and NORTHWESTSHELF-ANALYSIS-FORECAST-PHY-004-001_b

NORWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_		AMM7v9 PHYS_004_001_b	AMM15 PHY_004_013
Service	Entered Into Service	19/04/2017	18/11/2018

NORWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_		AMM7v9 PHYS_004_001_b	AMM15 PHY_004_013
Data Assimilation	NEMOVAR version	V3	V4
	SST bias correction scheme:	Offline observation-of-bias scheme. Reference dataset: in-situ.	Variational scheme in addition to observations-of-bias. Reference datasets: in-situ (drifters only) and VIIRS satellite data.
	Correlation operator short scale: 3-times grid scale	~20 km	~5 km

QUID for NWS MFC Products NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_004_013	Ref: CMEMS-NWS-QUID-004-013 Date: 10 Sep 2020 Issue: 1.3
---	--

NORWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_		AMM7v9 PHYS_004_001_b	AMM15 PHY_004_013
Model	Bathymetry	GEBCO corrected by NOOS partners	EMODnet 2015
	Horizontal resolution	7 km	1.5 km
	40°N- 65°N 20°W – 13°E Regular grid	~ 45°N - 63°N ~ 20°W - 13°E The grid has a rotated pole, chosen so that the grid-equator runs through the domain to reduce the distortion of cells with increasing latitude. While the rotated latitude is constant, the longitudinal grid steps range from ~1.47 km to 1.5 km.	40°N- 65°N 20°W – 13°E Regular grid
	Timestep	300 s (10 s barotropic sub-timestep)	60 s (~3.5 s barotropic sub-timestep)
	Penetrative radiation	1-band shortwave radiation light attenuation (as used in POLCOMS, Holt and James 2001)	NEMO tri-band Red-Blue-Green (RGB)
	Bottom friction	Log layer. Minimum drag coefficient 1.0×10^{-3}	Log layer. Minimum drag coefficient 2.5×10^{-3}
	Momentum diffusion	bi-Laplacian on model levels $1 \times 10^{10} \text{ m}^4/\text{s}$	bi-Laplacian on model levels $6 \times 10^7 \text{ m}^4/\text{s}$
	Tracer diffusion	Laplacian on geopotential levels $50 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$.	bi-Laplacian on model levels $1 \times 10^5 \text{ m}^4/\text{s}$

QUID for NWS MFC Products NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_004_013	Ref: CMEMS-NWS-QUID-004-013 Date: 10 Sep 2020 Issue: 1.3
---	--

NORWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_		AMM7v9 PHYS_004_001_b	AMM15 PHY_004_013
Forcing	Surface forcing	Met Office Global Unified Model (MetUM) Atmospheric model NWP analysis and forecast fields, calculated in the MetUM using COARE4 bulk formulae (Fairall et al. 2003).	ECMWF Integrated Forecasting System (IFS)- Atmospheric Model High Resolution (HRES) operational NWP forecast fields using CORE bulk formulae (Large and Yeager 2009)
	Surface forcing resolution	Horizontal grid: ~10 km (2560 x 1920 grid points) Frequency: 3 hourly mean fluxes of long and short wave radiation, moisture, 3 hourly mean air surface temperature but hourly 10 m winds and surface pressure	Horizontal grid: ~14 km (0.125°x0.125°). Frequency: 3 hourly instantaneous 2 m dew point temperature, surface pressure, mean sea level pressure, and 2 m air temperature. 3 hourly accumulated surface thermal and solar radiation, total precipitation, and total snow fall.
	Lateral boundaries	Met Office FOAM NATL (1/12°; 6 hourly fields) and CMEMS BALTICSEA (2 km, 1 hourly fields) AMM7v9 and AMM15 have Atlantic and Baltic boundaries in a different geographical location.	

QUID for NWS MFC Products NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_004_013	Ref: CMEMS-NWS-QUID-004-013 Date: 10 Sep 2020 Issue: 1.3
---	--

NORWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_		AMM7v9 PHYS_004_001_b	AMM15 PHY_004_013
Forcing	River run-off	Daily climatology of gauge data averaged for 1950–2005. Climatology of daily discharge data for 279 rivers from the Global River Discharge Data Base (Vörösmarty et al., 2000) and from data prepared by the Centre for Ecology and Hydrology as used by (Young and Holt, 2007).	Daily climatology of gauge data averaged for 1980–2014. UK data were processed from raw data provided by the Environment Agency, the Scottish Environment Protection Agency, the Rivers Agency (Northern Ireland), and the National River Flow Archive (personal communication by Sonja M. van Leeuwen, CEFAS, 2016). For major rivers that were missing from this data set (e.g. along the French and Norwegian coast), data have been provided by the same climatology used by AMM7 (Vörösmarty et al., 2000 and Young and Holt, 2007).

II.3.1 FOAM AMM15: model components, region, grid and bathymetry

The Forecasting Ocean Assimilation Model (FOAM) 1.5 km Atlantic Margin model (AMM15) is a hydrodynamic model, nested in a series of one-way nests to the Met Office global ocean model and the CMEMS Baltic model. The hydrodynamics are supplied by the Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean (NEMO) with the NEMOVAR 3D-Var FGAT system used for the assimilation of Sea Surface Temperature, Sea Level Anomaly, and temperature and salinity profiles data.

The ocean model is coupled, via OASIS with the wave model WaveWatch-III (see also CMEMS-NWS-QUID-004_014). The ocean-wave coupling has been implemented as described in Lewis et al. 2019 and includes three types of wave-current interactions:

- Modification of surface stress by wave growth and dissipation;
- Stokes-Coriolis forcing;
- Wave-height-dependent ocean surface roughness.

The model is located on the European North-West continental Shelf (NWS), from approximately 45°N to 63°N, and from 20°W to 11°E. The grid spacing is ~ 1.5 km in both the zonal and meridional direction (Graham et al. 2018).

The vertical coordinate system is based on a hybrid s -sigma terrain following system, $z^* - \sigma$ (Siddorn and Furner, 2013). The number of vertical levels is 51, as in the AMM7 model but some values have been tuned to take into account the increased resolution and the steeper gradients in the bathymetry. The thickness of the surface cell is set to ≤ 1 m to guarantee a uniform surface heat fluxes across the domain, as it is in AMM7.

The bathymetry (see Figure 2) is from EMODnet (EMODnet Portal, September 2015 release). This product is referenced to the Lowest Astronomical Tide (LAT) while the model needs the Mean Sea Level (MSL) referenced bathymetry. The differences between LAT and MSL referenced bathymetry are small in the deep ocean but not on shelf in the areas close to the coast, tidally dominated. Therefore, we had adjusted the bathymetry from LAT to MSL (Graham, 2018).

The original model grid is rotated but the CMEMS products are delivered on a regular grid at 1.5 km and 33 vertical levels, yellow box in Figure 2. The CMEMS products delivered by AMM15 covers a smaller area than AMM7v9, see Figure 2.

The depth in meters of the vertical levels are: 0, 3, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 40, 50, 60, 75, 100, 125, 150, 175, 200, 225, 250, 300, 350, 400, 450, 500, 550, 600, 750, 1000, 1500, 2000, 3000, 4000, 5000.

Figure 2: FOAM AMM15 bathymetry (m) showing the model domain (indicated by the shaded region). The yellow box is the domain covered by the regular grid AMM15 product delivered to CMEMS. The red line is the model and product domain of AMM7 (NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHYS_004_001_b. Figure modified from Graham et al. 2018.

<p style="text-align: center;">QUID for NWS MFC Products</p> <p style="text-align: center;">NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_004_013</p>	Ref:	CMEMS-NWS-QUID-004-013
	Date:	10 Sep 2020
	Issue:	1.3

II.3.2 Physical model

The FOAM system is based upon version 3.6 of the Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean (NEMO) code (Madec, 2016). This is a community model that has a wide user and developer base particularly in Europe. Tidal forcing is included both on the open boundary conditions via Flather radiation boundary conditions (Flather, 1976) and through the inclusion of equilibrium tide. The Topex Poseidon cross-over solution (Egbert and Erofeeva, 2002; TPX07.2, Atlantic Ocean 2011-ATLAS) provides 12 constituents for amplitude and phase of surface height and velocity at $1/12^\circ$. The model is one-way nested with the Met Office Operational North Atlantic $1/12^\circ$ deep ocean model (Storkey et al., 2010) and the Copernicus operational Baltic Sea model. They provide temperature, salinity, sea surface height (not at the Baltic boundary), depth integrated currents at the open boundaries.

Freshwater river fluxes are from a daily climatology of gauge data averaged for 1980–2014. UK data were processed from raw data provided by the Environment Agency, the Scottish Environment Protection Agency, the Rivers Agency (Northern Ireland), and the National River Flow Archive (personal communication by Sonja M. van Leeuwen, CEFAS, 2016). For major rivers that were missing from this data set (e.g. along the French and Norwegian coast), data have been provided by the same climatology used by AMM7 (Vörösmarty et al., 2000; and Young and Holt, 2007). Surface boundary conditions are provided by the European Centre for Middle-range Weather Forecast (ECMWF) using three hourly atmospheric forecast fields. This forcing is applied using the CORE bulk forcing algorithm (Large and Yeager, 2009). The light attenuation is set to the standard NEMO tri-band scheme (RGB), assuming a constant Chlorophyll concentration (Graham et al., 2018).

Tidal modelling requires a non-linear free surface and this is facilitated in NEMO by using a variable volume layer method. The short time scales associated with tidal propagation and the free surface require a time splitting approach, splitting modes into barotropic and baroclinic components. The bottom boundary condition includes a log layer representation and a k-epsilon turbulence scheme is implemented with a generic length scale (Umlauf and Burchard, 2003). The model uses a non-linear free surface, an energy and enstrophy conserving form of the momentum advection, and a free slip lateral momentum boundary condition. The tracer equation's use a TVD (Total Variance Dissipation) advection scheme (Zalesak, 1979). For tracer diffusion a Laplacian diffusion scheme on geopotential surfaces is applied, whereas for momentum diffusion a mixed Laplacian/bilaplacian scheme is used, with the Laplacian operator applied on geopotential surfaces and the bilaplacian on model surfaces.

II.3.3 Assimilation method

The data assimilation in AMM15 is very similar to data assimilation implemented in AMM7 (NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHYS_004_001_b). It uses NEMOVAR (Mogensen et al., 2012) which is an incremental 3D-Var, first guess at appropriate time (FGAT) assimilation scheme designed specifically for use with NEMO and further tuned at the Met Office for the $1/4^\circ$ global model (Waters et al., 2015) and the Atlantic Margin Model, AMM7 (King et al. 2018).

NEMOVAR version 4 is the assimilation scheme used by FOAM-AMM15 (Waters et al. 2015). The assimilation window is of 24-hours.

The assimilation scheme implemented in AMM15 is the same used by AMM7, described in King et al. 2018.

The observations used for the assimilation are in the table below (Table 3).

QUID for NWS MFC Products NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_004_013	Ref: CMEMS-NWS-QUID-004-013 Date: 10 Sep 2020 Issue: 1.3
---	--

Table 3: List of observations used for data assimilation

Type	Fields	Platforms/Satellite	Data source
IN SITU	SST Temperature and salinity profiles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ships • Drifters • Fixed moored arrays • Gliders • XBTs • CTDs • ARGO • Ferry boxes • Recopesca buoys* • Thermosalinograph 	GTS; http://www.wmo.int/pages/prog/ww/TEM/GTS CMEMS-INS-TAC : http://marine.copernicus.eu/ INSITU_GLO_NRT_OBSERVATIONS_013_030
SATELLITE	SLA Along Track* <i>*along with the corrections necessary for the use with a wind and pressure forced, tidal coastal model. SLA are assimilated only in deep regions (> 700 m).</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cryosat • Altika • Jason 3 • Sentinel 3 	CMEMS SL TAC: http://marine.copernicus.eu/ SEALEVEL_EUR_PHY_ASSIM_L3_NRT_OBSERVATIONS_008_043
	SST L2p/L3c	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NOAA-AVHRR • MetOp-AVHRR • SEVIRI • VIIRSG • AMSR2 	Group for High-Resolution Sea Surface Temperature (GHR SST) www.ghrsst.org

As detailed in King et al. (2018), the NEMOVAR system includes bias correction schemes for both SST and for altimeter data (using the CNES09 Mean Dynamic Topography of Rio et al. (2011) as a reference). The SLA bias correction is unchanged in AMM15. The AMM15 SST bias corrections is improved in AMM15. A variational data correction scheme is added to the observations-of-bias scheme to improve the SST bias correction. This new system is more resilient to changes in the observing system.

QUID for NWS MFC Products NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_004_013	Ref: CMEMS-NWS-QUID-004-013 Date: 10 Sep 2020 Issue: 1.3
---	--

III VALIDATION FRAMEWORK

Period of trial: 2 years, 1 January 2016 to 31 December 2017

Systems: AMM7v9 and AMM15, with and without Data Assimilation. The results discussed in this document are based on the experiments AMM7v9_DA and AMM15_DA.

System Name	Data Assimilated	Initial state	Forcing
AMM7v9 - FREE	N/A	restart from AMM7v9 operational	direct fluxes- MetOffice NWP
AMM7v9 -DA	DA: 3D SST, SLA, Sub-surface profiles	restart from AMM7v9 operational	direct fluxes- MetOffice NWP
AMM15v2 -FREE	N/A	restart from extension of the long simulation (Graham et , 2018)	bulk - ECMWF OP
AMM15v2 -DA	DA: 3D SST, SLA, Sub-surface profiles (same set of observations used form AMM7v9 exp)	restart from extension of the long simulation (Graham et, 2018)	bulk - ECMWF OP

QUID for NWS MFC Products NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_004_013	Ref: CMEMS-NWS-QUID-004-013 Date: 10 Sep 2020 Issue: 1.3
---	--

III.1 Summary of tested metrics

Table 4: List of tested metrics

Variable	Description	Supporting observations	Class	Metrics
Tidal harmonics	European coasts	Tide gauges data	4	Amplitude and phase: scatterplots, co-tidal charts, mean error (model-observation) and RMSD.
SST	whole region	OSTIA L4 SST analysis	1	Bias (observation-model), RMSD
	Shelf, whole region	In-situ (buoys and ships of opportunity)	1 and 4	Bias (observation-model), RMSD
Temperature and salinity profiles	whole domain; sub regions	Profile data available over GTS; glider data not assimilated; mooring in the German Bight	4	Bias (Observation-model), RMSD, time series (only for moorings in the German Bight, and gliders)
Kara mixed layer depth	whole domain; sub regions	EN4 dataset; glider data not assimilated	4	Bias (Observation-model); RMSD, time series (only for gliders)
Surface velocity	Sub-region (German bight)	COSYNA HF - radar	4	Bias (Observation-model); RMSD, correlation, maps

IV VALIDATION RESULTS

IV.1 Observations used for the validation

The observations used for the validation of the experiments are:

- Set of observations (in situ, see Figure 3, and satellite, Figure 5) used by the data assimilation, see Table 4. These measurements are considered semi-independent because even if the misfit (observation-model) is computed before the model is corrected by the data assimilation, there is a dependency between model-observations due to the previous data assimilation cycles. L4 SST product, OSTIA (SST_GLO_SST_L4_NRT_OBSERVATIONS_010_001) is not assimilated into the model but most of the in-situ and satellite measurements used by OSTIA are assimilated by AMM7 and AMM15.
- Independent observations, not used by data assimilation (Figure 4 and Figure 8):
 - Glider transect from the UK MASSMO4 experiments (north of Scotland);
 - COSYNA HF radar in the German Bight
 - Tide gauges
 - Moorings in the German Bight

Figure 3: Total number of temperature (left) and salinity (right) profiles in 2-degree bins for 2016-2017. Top panel: observations distribution in winter (December-January-February, DJF). Bottom panel: observations distribution in summer (June-July-August, JJA).

QUID for NWS MFC Products NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_004_013	Ref:	CMEMS-NWS-QUID-004-013
	Date:	10 Sep 2020
	Issue:	1.3

Figure 4: Maps of the independent observations used for validation. MASSMO4 Gliders are blue, COSYNA HF in the German Bight in green and the mooring in the German Bight in red.

Figure 5: Number of observations (2016-2017) used by the data assimilation and by the validation. SST (in situ and satellite), left panel. Satellite SLA right panel.

IV.2 Bathymetry

AMM15 has a better representation of the bathymetry than AMM7. This is due to the original data used for the model bathymetry and to the improved horizontal resolution which allow a much more realistic representation of the seafloor.

Figure 6 shows the two models bathymetry on shelf. AMM15 resolves small structures, and small-scale variability not resolved by AMM7. E.g., the complex variability of the bathymetry is better represented in the south west edge of the Celtic Sea and in the Irish Sea.

Figure 6: Model bathymetry on shelf. Left: AMM7, right: AMM15.

IV.3 Tidal harmonics

IV.3.1 Comparison with tide gauges

A harmonic analysis of the dominant tidal constituents was compared against tide gauge observations from BODC (British Oceanographic Data Center). While the performance of AMM7 and AMM15 is similar (Figure 7), anomaly varies across the domain (Figure 8), showing regional improvements (Graham et al. 2018). The number of tide gauges taken into consideration for AMM15 and AMM7 is the same, therefore the most coastal buoys, not resolved by the AMM7 coastline are not taken into consideration. AMM15 has a high horizontal resolution but since the model applies a minimum depth of 10 m, the inaccuracy in depth can affect the capability to properly estimate the tidal speed very close to the coast (Graham et al. 2018).

Tidal amplitude 2017 [cm]

Tidal phase 2017 [deg]

Figure 7: RMSD and bias (observation-model) of the tidal amplitude (top panel) and phase (bottom panel) of the prevalent tidal constituents. AMM15 is in red (dotted line bias, full line RMSD) and AMM7 in blue (dotted line bias, full line RMSD). The values are means of all the available tide gauges.

Figure 8: M2 phase (left) and amplitude (right) error relative to observations for AMM15 (observation-model).

Figure 8 shows the spatial distribution of the M2 tidal errors in AMM15. The values of RMS and mean error for amplitude and phase are very similar in AMM15 and AMM7. The M2 amplitude tends to be somewhat underestimate in the south-west part of the North Sea and along the east coast of UK. Phase errors are largest in the southern North Sea and off the north-eastern coast of Northern Ireland.

Figure 9: M2 amplitude (left) and phase (right) observations versus model values.

Figure 9 compares the model against observations for both the M2 amplitude (cm) and phase (degrees).

The co-tidal chart for M2 (Figure 10) compares very well with observations (see comparable chart in Howarth and Pugh, 1983). The differences between AMM15 and AMM7 systems are very small (co-tidal map of AMM7 not shown).

Figure 10; Co-tidal chart for M2 component, AMM15.

IV.3.2 Comparison with HF Radar

The HF radar data used here are one month, March 2017, of total surface velocity currents estimated from 3 WERA HF radar systems deployed in the German Bight (Gurgel et al., 2011) as part of the COSYNA (Coastal Observing System for Northern and Arctic Seas) observing network (Figure 4). Data are available through the EMODnet Physics data portal. At the operating frequencies used, the total surface velocities represent an integrated velocity over a depth between 1 and 2 m. The HF radar data are averaged every 20 minutes on a grid of resolution of ~3 km.

Because the high frequency variability of the flow in the German bight is dominated by tidal flow, a low pass filter was used to separate the tidal and the residual component of the velocity. Statistics were computed on the high-pass (Figure 11 and Figure 12) and low-pass (Figure 28) filtered velocity components to assess the tidal and residual flow respectively. Vector correlation (or complex correlation of $u+iv$, where u and v are the zonal and meridional velocity respectively, and i is the square root of -1) were estimated and are displayed as correlation amplitude, and phase, or veering. The phase represents the rotation between the two vectors that gives the highest correlation.

The various metrics show that AMM15 resolved the tidal current in the south German Bight better than AMM7, as shown in Figure 11. Although AMM15 bias is slightly higher than AMM17 in some areas, RMSD of AMM15 is smaller than the RMSD of AMM7 everywhere in the HF radar domain.

Figure 11: plots of statistics between HF radar surface current observations and AMM7 (left) and AMM15 (right) for the high-passed filtered data (tidal signal). Bias (observation-model) and RMSD (in m/s) are estimated on the velocity vector magnitudes.

Both models show high correlation with the observations and AMM15 has a lower phase with the observations. Because tidal velocities are rotating periodic signals, the spatial angular veering

estimated using the complex correlation can also be interpreted as a temporal phase of the tidal signal. Positive veering angle means that the model tidal velocities lead the HF radar tidal velocities. Figure 12 shows that the phase of the tide is improved in AMM15 compared to AMM7 in most of the domain, consistent with the results of IV.3.1.

Figure 12: plots of vector correlation amplitude (top) and phase or veering (bottom). Positive (negative) veering represent a clockwise (counter-clockwise) angle of AMM15 vectors with respect to the HF radar vectors.

QUID for NWS MFC Products NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_004_013	Ref:	CMEMS-NWS-QUID-004-013
	Date:	10 Sep 2020
	Issue:	1.3

IV.4 Sea surface temperature (SST)

IV.4.1 Comparison with in-situ

SST data is assimilated in the AMM15 model (Figure 5) during the Incremental Analysis Update (IAU) step of each model run. As result, an assessment of the model skill at predicting SST compared to observations would be expected to produce positive result. Model SST has been assesses here against in-situ SST measurements using the Met Office’s obs_stat package. This package uses the model to observation matchups created before the SST data has been assimilated. The matchups are created by interpolating the model field to the observation location at the time of the observations. The in-situ measurements are from buoys and ship of opportunity. The top plot of Figure 13 shows a time series of daily observation minus model RMS error (solid line) and mean error/bias (dashed line) for the whole AMM15 domain; the AMM15 system is black and the AMM7 is blue. The bottom plot shows the number of in-situ observations used per day for the assessment period. The differences between the two systems are very small. The RMSD is ~0.5°C for both AMM7 and AMM15. Both systems have a small warm bias, -0.01°C, over the full period. The warm bias is mainly due to the winter months when the model is slightly warmer than the observations. The same statics on-shelf shows very similar results.

Figure 13: Observation minus model SST daily assessment of AMM15 (black) and AMM7 (blue) against in-situ observations (top plot) and number of observations per day (bottom plot) for the whole domain. In the top-plot, the mean error (observation-model) is shown by the dashed line (a positive value indicates a cold model bias) and the RMSD error is shown by the solid line

<p style="text-align: center;">QUID for NWS MFC Products</p> <p style="text-align: center;">NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_004_013</p>	<p>Ref:</p> <p>Date:</p> <p>Issue:</p>	<p>CMEMS-NWS-QUID-004-013</p> <p>10 Sep 2020</p> <p>1.3</p>
--	--	---

IV.4.2 Variability in SST against in situ

A small number of buoy locations have been compared to investigate the SST variability in the models (see Figure 4). Three sites were investigated in this study, E1 (50.026°N, 4.225°W) in the English Channel and the FINO sites in the German Bight (FINO1 at 54° 00.89 N, E 6°35.26 E and FINO3 at 55°11.7 N 7°9.5 E). In future it would be helpful to get a broader range of sites included.

A Butterworth filter has been applied to the hourly SST to remove low frequency (periods greater than 5 days) signals in the SST timeseries, to allow a comparison of the high frequency changes only. The observation data was interpolated to the hour to be equivalent to the model data, and the precision of the model data reduced to the same precision as the observations, to allow direct comparison and to prevent any aliasing. The timeseries is divided in seasons, both due to the high seasonal variability of SST and to avoid observation data gaps that would skew the analysis. We defined the four seasons as: December-January-February (DJF), March-April-May (MAM), June-July-August (JJA), and September, October, November (SON). The data used for this study covers the period December 2016-November 2017. Spectral power were smoothed using a Loess filter to remove noise in the spectra. The non-filtered spectra are also plotted as faint lines.

The model data was taken from the analysis day. It would be interesting to also assess the forecast, but sufficient periods of forecast are not available. Figure 14 shows the SST and filtered SST timeseries at the FINO3 mooring for two different seasons, winter (DJF) and summer (JJA). The filtered SST signal has a higher variability in summer when the diurnal warming is stronger and therefore the SST gradients are bigger. AMM7 and AMM15 have a very similar value of SST, probably due to the data assimilation of SST that bring both models close to the observations.

Figure 14: Timeseries of sea surface temperature (left) and filtered SST (right) for the FINO 3 buoy for December 2016-February 2017 (top) and June-August 2017 (bottom).

Figure 15 shows the power spectra for seasons for the FINO 3 buoys. The power spectra in the other moorings location, E1 and FINO1, is not shown but is similar to FINO3. Although this is not exclusively true, the general trend is for the models to drop off in power more quickly, and have a steeper spectral slope, than the observations. The AMM15 almost always has more power in the 4 to 6 hour period of the spectrum, and is more close to the observations. At higher frequencies (shorter periods) the models collapse to the same power spectrum, which has generally (but not exclusively) lower power than that of the observations.

Figure 15: Power spectrum of SST for the FINO3 buoy compared with the AMM7 (blue) and AMM15 (red) simulations for December 2016 to February 2017 (top left), March to May 2017 (top right), June to August 2017 (bottom left) and September to November 2017 (bottom right).

This is consistent both with what one would expect of the mesoscale resolving AMM15, and with what one can see by qualitative inspection of the model fields, in that this represents higher frequency, small length scale features being more prevalent in the AMM15. It also suggests that on average some of the very high frequency / small scale features are still not being represented in the models, although it should be noted that the model represents a mean over a grid which will by definition introduce some smoothing, whereas the observations are (at least to a greater extent) sampling at a point.

From this analysis we demonstrate quantitatively what is obvious from looking at the fields – that the AMM15 better represents the high frequency / small scale features seen in the ocean than its predecessor. This result is likely to be even more pronounced in forecast fields, although that is not demonstrated here.

QUID for NWS MFC Products NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_004_013	Ref:	CMEMS-NWS-QUID-004-013
	Date:	10 Sep 2020
	Issue:	1.3

IV.4.3 Comparison to OSTIA

In addition to the in-situ observation assessment, the models SSTs have been compared to the Met Office’s Operational Sea surface Temperature and sea Ice Analysis (OSTIA) system (Donlon, et al., 2012). OSTIA provides analyses of the foundation SST (i.e. the SST free of diurnal variability) and assimilates in-situ and satellite observations. The OSTIA data are available through the CMEMS catalogue as product SST_GLO_SST_L4_NRT_OBSERVATIONS_010_001. OSTIA is produced on a 1/20°grid (~6 km resolution), however, this is not the feature resolution of the product, which depends on other aspects of the system such as the correlation length scales used in producing the analysis. OSTIA has a maximum feature resolution of ~20-30 km and so both AMM7 and much more AMM15 are expected to represent smaller features than OSTIA.

The important point to consider in this assessment is that OSTIA foundation SST is being compared to the model surface box daily mean SST that should be biased warm compare to foundation.

The bias is observation-model. AMM7 and AMM15 have a negative bias (Figure 16), therefore the model is bias warm compare to OSTIA, as expected. AMM15 has a slightly higher bias than AMM7 and this could due to the methodology used for the inter-comparison of the three dataset with OSTIA and AMM15 interpolated on AMM7 grid. The high variability of the signal in AMM15 is therefore penalized by this analysis. Overall we see little differences in performances between the two systems.

Figure 16: Model SST minus OSTIA RMD and bias daily comparison for AMM7 (blue) and AMM15 (red) for the whole domain (negative mean error indicates a warm model bias).

IV.5 Temperature and salinity profiles

AMM15 resolved better the vertical structure of the water column and has a lower bias and RMSD compared to AMM7 in salinity and temperature. Figure 17 shows the mean error (obs-model) and the RMSD compute before the assimilation of the vertical profiles. The differences in temperature at surface are very small between the two models but between 500 and 1000 m AMM15 has an error mean close to zero. AMM15 has also a lower RMSD below the surface. AMM15 has at all depth but the surface a better RMSD in salinity. The distribution of the observations show in Figure 3, is uneven, with very few observations on shelf.

Figure 17: Observation minus model temperature (left) and salinity (right) profile assessment for AMM15 (black) and AMM7 (blue) for the whole domain (left plot). The RMS difference is shown by the solid lines and bias (observation-model) is shown by the dashed lines.

Figure 18 instead shows the statistics compared during year 2017 at the moorings in the German Bight (Figure 4). Observations are available for both temperature and salinity at surface (5 m) and bottom. The models assimilate only the SST observation, not the salinity and the temperature at bottom. The hourly instantaneous model data are compared to the buoy observations during year 2017. Some moorings have short discontinuity in the measurements during the year. AMM15 has a better RMSD and a lower error mean at each buoy location. The high frequency variability is better reproduced by AMM15 than AMM7, as shown in Figure 19 and Figure 20.

Figure 18: Observation-model as yearly mean RMSD and BIAS at the 5 moorings in the German Bight. Temperature (left) and salinity (right) at the surface and at the bottom. The red line is AMM15, the blue line is AMM7.

Figure 19: Sea bottom temperature at the FINO3 mooring for year 2017. AMM15 red line, AMM7 blue line, observations black line.

Figure 20: Sea surface salinity at the NsbII mooring for year 2017. AMM15 red line, AMM7 blue line, observations black line.

AMM15 and AMM7 vertical structure and high frequency variability is assessed against the glider profiles from MASSMO4 (Figure 4 and Figure 21). AMM15 is in very well agreement with the observations and shows good improvement, compare to AMM7, in particular in the salinity (Figure 22 and Figure 23). The density of the water column during the period of the gliders campaign is much more accurate in AMM15 (Figure 24). These results are very encouraging even if are not representative of the whole model domain and of the seasonal variability in stratification of the water column.

In all the pictures of AMM7, there is a blob of high anomaly close to the bottom on the 23/05. This is due to the model bathymetry, shallower than the reality in that specific location. AMM15 instead has a more realistic representation of the sea bottom (see IV.2).

QUID for NWS MFC Products NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_004_013	Ref:	CMEMS-NWS-QUID-004-013
	Date:	10 Sep 2020
	Issue:	1.3

Figure 21: Glider 553-100 trajectory. The glider started the measurement close to the Scotland coast, then moved towards the shelf break.

Figure 22: Temperature profile along glider 553-100 trajectory. Top panel: temperature measured by the Glider. Bottom left: difference glider-AMM15. Bottom right: difference glider-AMM7. The vertical blue line represents when the glider goes over the shelf break, crossing the 200 m isobath. Before that time the glider is on the shelf.

QUID for NWS MFC Products NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_004_013	Ref:	CMEMS-NWS-QUID-004-013
	Date:	10 Sep 2020
	Issue:	1.3

Figure 23: Salinity profile along glider 553-100 trajectory. Top panel: salinity measured by the Glider. Bottom left: difference glider-AMM15. Bottom right: difference glider-AMM7. The vertical blue line represents when the glider goes over the shelf break, crossing the 200 m isobath. Before that time the glider is on the shelf.

Figure 24: Density profile along glider 553-100 trajectory. Top panel: salinity measured by the Glider. Bottom left: difference glider-AMM15. Bottom right: difference glider-AMM7. The vertical blue line represents when the glider goes over the shelf break, crossing the 200 m isobath. Before that time the glider is on the shelf.

IV.6 Mixed Layer Depth

The mixed layer depth has been calculated within the model using a density criteria, following the definition of Kara et al. (2000) except the reference depth of 10 m is changed to 3 m (due to the shallower regions of the continental shelf). The MLD is defined as the depth where the density increase, compared to density at 3 m depth, corresponds to a temperature decrease of 0.2°C in local surface conditions. The EN4 (Good et al., 2013) profile dataset of temperature and salinity (see Figure 25) was used to calculate an ‘observed’ Kara mixed layer depth following the same procedure used within the model.

Figure 25: Left panel: spatial distribution of the N4 observations used for the MLD computation. Right panel: AMM15 Kara mixed layer depth bias (red dashed) and RMSD (blue solid). A positive mean error value indicates a model over-estimate. A positive bias value indicates a model under-estimation of the MLD

An important point to note here is that on a daily/monthly timescale the EN4 dataset is still relatively sparse in the region of interest and often clustered in particularly locations. This is particularly true on the continental shelf. Assessing the model as a whole we see a seasonal cycle of errors with small errors in summer/autumn (bias ~10 m and RMSD < 25 m) and larger errors in winter/spring.

Gliders data from the UK experiment MASSMO4 are available north of Scotland from 22nd May till 6th June 2017 (see Figure 4). Figure 21 to Figure 26 show the trajectories of the three gliders during the experiment. The gliders have been deployed close to the coast and then travelled across the shelf break. We have computed, the mixed layer depth from the observations and compared the mixed layer depth from the gliders with AMM15 and AMM7 in the match up locations. AMM15 reproduces better than AMM7 the mixed layer depth and represents very well the variability of the signal. Figure 26 shows the mixed layer depth along the glider transect 553 computed from the observations and from the model. AMM15 shows a much better representation of the signal and of its variability. This positive result is confirmed along the trajectories of the three gliders.

Figure 26: Mixed layer depth along the Glider 553 transect. Black line: glider observation, red AMM15, blue AMM7. The vertical blue line represents when the glider goes over the shelf break, crossing the 200 m isobath. Before that time the glider is on the shelf.

IV.7 Sea Surface Height

AMM15 and AMM7 SSH is assessed against the satellite Sea Level Anomaly data used for the data assimilation (see Figure 5). It's worth to note that the assimilation of SLA is done only where the bathymetry is deeper than 700 m, therefore no observations are assimilated on shelf and in large part of the off-shelf region. The differences between AMM15 and AM7 are negligible both on the continental shelf and off shelf, Figure 27. As expected in a tidally dominated area, on the continental shelf the RMSD is higher than off shelf.

Figure 27: Observation minus model SSH daily assessment of AMM15 (black) and AMM7 (blue) against satellite observations (top plot of each panel) and number of observations per day (bottom plot of each panel) for the continental shelf region (top panel) and the off shelf (bottom panel). The mean error is shown by the dashed line and the RMS error is shown by the solid line.

IV.8 Surface currents

There are very few measurements of velocity in this area (Figure 4). Among the few data available we have decided to use the surface currents measured by the HF radar.

The HF radar data used here are one month of total surface velocity currents estimated from 3 WERA HF radar systems deployed in the German Bight (Gurgel et al., 2011). Data are available through the EMODnet Physics data portal. At the operating frequencies used, the total surface velocities represent an integrated velocity over a depth between 1 and 2 m. The HF radar data are averaged every 20 minutes on a grid of resolution of ~3 km.

Because the high frequency variability of the flow in the German bight is dominated by tidal flow, a low pass filter was used to separate the tidal and the residual component of the velocity. Statistics we computed on the high-pass and low-pass filtered velocity components to assess the tidal and residual flow respectively. The assessment of the tidal flow is described in section IV.3.2.

AMM15 shows a clear improvement, with much better defined surface currents, as shown in Figure 28.

Figure 28: March 2017 average surface flow for HF radar (top), AMM7 (middle) and AMM15 (bottom), from Tonani et al. (2019). Model data are re-gridded on the HF radar grid using cubic interpolation. The hourly model outputs are linearly interpolated every minute to match the HF radar observations. Model output are only plotted where HF radar data are available.

<p style="text-align: center;"> QUID for NWS MFC Products NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_004_013 </p>	<p>Ref:</p> <p>Date:</p> <p>Issue:</p>	<p>CMEMS-NWS-QUID-004-013</p> <p>10 Sep 2020</p> <p>1.3</p>
--	--	---

IV.9 SST forecast skills

North West-European Shelf SST data have been used for assessing forecasts skills, inter-comparing the low resolution (7km, 004_001_b) and the high-resolution (1.5km, 004_013) product.

For the purpose of this assessment, the 5 d daily mean potential SST forecasts (with lead times of 12, 36, 60, 84 and 108 h) were utilised for the period from January to September 2019. Forecasts were compared for the co-located areas of AMM7 and AMM15. The study of Crocker et al., 2020 describes the spatial techniques used for assessing the forecast accuracy and skill across models with different resolution.

The paper Croker et al. (<https://doi.org/10.5194/os-16-831-2020>) describes the methodology and all the results showing a large reduction (improvement) in errors for AMM15 when going from a grid-scale, point-based verification assessment to a neighbourhood, ensemble approach. When applying an equivalent-sized neighbourhood to both configurations, AMM15 typically demonstrated lower (better) scores (Croker et al. 2020).

QUID for NWS MFC Products NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_004_013	Ref: CMEMS-NWS-QUID-004-013 Date: 10 Sep 2020 Issue: 1.3
---	--

V SYSTEM'S NOTICEABLE EVENTS, OUTAGES OR CHANGES

N/A the system is new.

Date	Change/Event description	System version	other
15/12/2020	Direct two-way coupling between wave and physical ocean models.	AMM15v1.3	

QUID for NWS MFC Products NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_004_013	Ref: CMEMS-NWS-QUID-004-013 Date: 10 Sep 2020 Issue: 1.3
---	--

VI QUALITY CHANGES SINCE PREVIOUS VERSION

VI.1 Impact to physical model from physical ocean-wave coupling (Dec 2020)

Following the December 2020 product release, physical ocean analysis-forecast products are delivered by a two-way coupled ocean-wave model system, using the coupler OASIS3-MCT.

The ocean-wave coupling has been implemented as described in Lewis et al. 2019 and includes three wave-currents interactions:

- Modification of surface stress by wave growth and dissipation;
- Stokes-Coriolis forcing;
- Wave-height-dependent ocean surface roughness.

The major impact of the coupling has been proven to be on the currents, with an improved accuracy of currents during storm events of 3% off shelf and ~8% on-shelf (VI.1.1). The impact on the other variables is neutral.

VI.1.1 Details on the current validation

We have done a study on the impact of the ocean-wave coupling on the currents using Isphere and SVP drifter data during the most important storms of year 2016. The wave-current interactions are enhanced during storm events when the Stokes' drift can reach values higher than the ocean currents off-shelf and significantly modifies the strong tidal currents on-shelf.

Drifter trajectories were simulated using OpenDrift Lagrangian framework (Dagestad et al., 2018; Dagestad and Rohrs, 2019). The model surface currents have been used for simulating ishere drifter trajectories, currents at 15m have been used for the SVP drifter with a drogoue. The evaluation of the model trajectories is done using a skill sore (SS) that evaluated the separation between drifter and model trajectories:

$$SS = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N d_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=0}^i l_{oi}}$$

$i, j=0 \dots N$ identify measurements at different times along a trajectory;

l_{oi} is the length of the observed trajectory at time t_i ;

d_i is the distance between the observed and the simulated drifter position at time t_i ;

N is the total number of observed drifter positions;

$N=1$ is a tolerance threshold.

QUID for NWS MFC Products NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_004_013	Ref:	CMEMS-NWS-QUID-004-013
	Date:	10 Sep 2020
	Issue:	1.3

The summary results of the SS values for all the storms considered in this study, show that the coupled system improves the accuracy of the currents on shelf and off-shelf. The validation is done for the currents at surface where Isphere drifter were available and at 15m for SVP drifter with a drogue.

Model vs. Drifters

Model variable	Region	SS ensemble mean		# obs
		not cpl	cpl	
surface currents	on-shelf	▼ 0.76 ±.01	▲ 0.82 ±.01	10
	off-shelf	▼ 0.58 ±.01	▲ 0.61 ±.01	22
currents at 15m	on-shelf	▼ 0.37 ±.02	▲ 0.53 ±.01	2
	off-shelf	▼ 0.43 ±.02	▲ 0.46 ±.01	16

Figure 29: Trajectories simulation during storm Jake (left) and storm Gertrude (right). The black line represents the drifter trajectory, the trajectory computed using the ocean currents and the Stokes drift from a non-coupled ocean and wave models are in blue, from a coupled ocean-wave is red.

VI.2 Impact of changes between 7 km and 1.5 km resolution (Nov 2018)

This is the first release of the products from the 1.5 km system. NWS-MFC continues to deliver analysis and forecast products from both AMM7 (product 004_001_b) and AMM15 (product 004_013). The differences in the two products and system are:

- Model resolution.
- Bathymetry.
- Geographical location of the lateral boundaries in the Baltic Sea and in the Atlantic Ocean.
- Atmospheric forcing (AMM15 is forced by ECMWF forecast fields, AMM7 from UK Met office analysis/forecast fields).

QUID for NWS MFC Products NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_004_013	Ref:	CMEMS-NWS-QUID-004-013
	Date:	10 Sep 2020
	Issue:	1.3

VII REFERENCES

Crocker R., Maksymczuk J., Mittermaier M., Tonani M. and Pequignet, A.C. (2020) An approach to the verification of high-resolution ocean models using spatial methods, *Ocean sci.*, 16, 831-845, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.5194/os-16-831-2020>

Dagestad, K.-F., and J. Rohrs (2019), Prediction of ocean surface trajectories using satellite derived vs. modeled ocean currents, *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 223, 130–142, doi:10.1016/j.rse.2019.01.001.

Dagestad, K.-F., J. Rohrs, . Breivik, and B. Adlandsvik (2018), OpenDrift v1.0: a generic framework for trajectory modelling, *Geoscientific Model Development*, 11(4), 1405–1420, doi:10.5194/gmd-11-1405-2018.

Donlon C.J., Martin M., Stark J., Roberts-Jones J., Fiedler E., Wimmer W., (2012) The Operational Sea Surface Temperature and Sea Ice Analysis (OSTIA) system, *Remote sensing of Environment*, 116, 140-158.

Flather, R.A., (1976): A tidal model of the north west European continental shelf. *Memoires de la Societe Royale de Sciences de Liege*, 6, 141-164.

Flather R. A. (1981). "Results from a model of the north east Atlantic relating to the Norwegian Coastal Current". *The Norwegian Coastal Current (Proceedings from the...symposium, Geilo, 9-12 September 1980)*. Bergen: Bergen University, 2, 427-458

Graham J., E. O’Dea, J. Holt, J. Polton, H. T. Hewitt, R. Furner, K. Guihou, A. Breerton, A. Arnold, S. Wakelin, J-M Castillo Sanchez, C. G. Mayorga Adame, (2018) A new high resolution ocean configuration for operational simulation of the European North West Shelf, *Geosci. Model Dev.*, 11, 681-696.

Good S.A., Martin M.A., and Rayner N.A., (2013) EN4: quality controlled ocean temperature and salinity profiles and monthly objective analyses with uncertainty estimates, *JGR: Oceans*, 118, 6704-7616.

Gurgel, K. W., Schlick, T., Voulgaris, G., Seemann, J., & Ziemer, F. (2011, March). HF radar observations in the German Bight: Measurements and quality control. In *Current, Waves and Turbulence Measurements (CWTM)*, 2011 IEEE/OES 10th (pp. 51-56). IEEE.

<p style="text-align: center;">QUID for NWS MFC Products</p> <p style="text-align: center;">NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_004_013</p>	Ref:	CMEMS-NWS-QUID-004-013
	Date:	10 Sep 2020
	Issue:	1.3

Howarth, M.J. and D.T. Pugh (1983). Observations of tides over the continental shelf of northwest Europe. In *Physical Oceanography of the Coastal and Shelf Seas*, Johns B, Ed. Elsevier, Amsterdam, pp.133-85.

Kara, A. B., P. A. Rochford, and H. E. Hurlburt (2000), An optimal definition for ocean mixed layer depth, *J. Geophys. Res.*, 105(C7), 16803–16821, doi:10.1029/2000JC900072.

King R., J. While, M. J. Martin, D. J. Lea, B. Lemieux-Dudon, j. Waters, E. O’Dea, 2018. Improving the initialisation of the Met Office operational shelf-seas model. *Ocean Modelling*, vol. 130, pages 1-14.

Large W. and Yeager S., 2009. The global climatology of an interannually varying air-sea data set, *Climate Dynamics*. 33, 341-364.

Lewis, H., Castillo Sanchez, J. M., Siddorn, J., King, R., Tonani, M., Saulter, A., Sykes, P., Péquignot, A.-C., Weedon, G., Palmer, T., Staneva, J., and Bricheno, L.: Can wave coupling improve operational regional ocean forecasts for the North-West European Shelf, *Ocean Sci.*, 15, 669–690, <https://doi.org/10.5194/os-15-669-2019>, 2019.

Madec, G. and the NEMO team (2016) NEMO ocean engine. Note du Pôle de modélisation, Institut Pierre-Simon Laplace (IPSL), France, No 27 ISSN No 1288-1619.

Morgensen K, Balmaseda M.A., Weaver A., 2012. The NEMOVAR ocean data assimilation system as implemented in the ECMWF ocean analysis for System 4. European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts.

Rio M.H., Guinehut S., Larnicol G., 2011. New CNES-CLS09 global mean dynamic topography computed from the combination of GRACE data, altimetry and in situ measurements. *J. Geophys. Res.* 116, C)7018+.

Siddorn, J., Furner R. (2013): An analytical stretching function that combines the best attributes of geopotential and terrain-following vertical coordinates, *Ocean Modelling*, 66, 1-13

Storkey, D., Blockley, E. W., Furner, R., Guiavarc’h, C., Lea, D., Martin, M. J., Barciela, R. M., Hines, A., Hyder, P., and Siddorn, J. R.: Forecasting the ocean state using NEMO: The new FOAM system, *J. Oper. Oceanogr.*, 3, 3–15, 2010.

<p style="text-align: center;">QUID for NWS MFC Products</p> <p style="text-align: center;">NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_004_013</p>	<p>Ref:</p> <p>Date:</p> <p>Issue:</p>	<p>CMEMS-NWS-QUID-004-013</p> <p>10 Sep 2020</p> <p>1.3</p>
--	--	---

Tonani, M., Sykes, P., King, R.R., McConnell, N., Pequignet, A.C., O’Dea, E., Graham, J.A., Polton, J., and Siddorn, J. (2019). The impact of a new high-resolution ocean model on the Met Office North-West European Shelf forecasting system, *Ocean Sci.*, 15, 1133–1158, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.5194/os-15-1133-2019>.

Umlauf, L., Burchard, H., (2003). A generic length-scale equation for geophysical turbulence models. *Journal of Marine Research* 61, 235–265.

Vörösmarty, J., P. Green, J. Salisbury, R. B. Lammers (2000) Global Water Resources: Vulnerability from Climate Change and Population Growth. *Science* 289, 284-288; DOI: 10.1126/science.289.5477.284.

Waters, J., Daniel J. Lea, Matthew J. Martin, Isabelle Mirouze, Anthony Weaver and James While, (2015). Implementing a variational data assimilation system in an operational 1/4 degree global ocean model. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc.*141: 333 – 349, January 2015 B DOI:10.1002/qj.2388

Young, E. F., Holt, J. T.: Prediction and analysis of long-term variability of temperature and salinity in the Irish Sea.(2007) *JGR Oceans*, Vol. 112, C1, 1-18, doi:10.1029/2005JC003386,

Zalesak, S. T., (1979) Fully Multidimensional Flux-Corrected Transport Algorithms for Fluids, *J. Comput. Phys.*, 31, 335–362.